

UNIVERSITY OF ICELAND

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

Gender-based violence (GBV) has been on the agenda in Icelandic universities for a long time. All seven universities in Iceland are required to have a Gender Equality Plan, in accordance with Act No. 1050/2020 on Equal Status and Equal Rights Irrespective of Gender (and Act No. 96/2000 on the Equal Status and Equal Rights of Women and Men). Moreover, Act No. 46/1980 on the Working Environment, Health and Safety in Workplaces and Regulation No. 1009/2015 on Measures against Bullying, Sexual Harassment, Gender-Based Harassment and Violence in Workplaces require universities, as well as other employers, to provide a safe and healthy working environment. Many universities employ professional counsellors to respond to GBV. GBV is also a regular topic at the 'Equality Days' festival that has been held annually by the University of Iceland since 2009¹ and by all Icelandic universities since 2015.² Nonetheless, the first #MeToo movement in 2017, and specifically the movement among women in the sciences, called on universities to take further action. Women in the sciences started a petition to demand that the academic community end gender and sexual harassment and violence that thrives in the community. They also published 106 anonymous statements about experiences of GBV in the academic community.³

¹ https://english.hi.is/university/equality_days

² <https://www.ru.is/skipulag/samfelagsabyrgd/jafnrettisdagar/>

³ <https://www.visir.is/g/20171884043d>

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

The University of Iceland has implemented **three** policies and strategies that address GBV. Two of them are dedicated GBV policies and one is a more general document that addresses GBV: the Equality Action Plan 2021-2023,⁴ Rules of Procedure on the Response to Gender-Related and Sexual Harassment and Other Sexual Violence⁵ (hereinafter called the Rules of Procedure), and the #MeToo Action Plan.⁶

The Equal Rights Committee oversees matters of equality at the University of Iceland.⁷ The equality officer, a role shared by two employees,⁸ supervises the University of Iceland's Equality Action Plan in collaboration with the Equal Rights Committee. A major stakeholder regarding GBV is the University Professional Council, which works in accordance with the Rules of Procedure.

URLs

- › The Equality Action Plan:
https://english.hi.is/university/university_of_iceland_equality_action_plan
- › Rules of Procedure on the Response to Gender-Related and Sexual Harassment and Other Sexual Violence:
https://english.hi.is/university/rules_of_procedure_on_the_response_to_gender_related_and_sexual_harassment_and_other
- › #MeToo 'In the shadow of power relations: women in sciences', University of Iceland's Action Plan - not published.

Entry into force: The Equality Action Plan entered into force in **2021**, the two other policies in **2018**.

TRAINING

Prevention and protection measures include training for students, staff, managers, and subcontracted staff. Key players and the equality officers in the management are responsible for developing and delivering those trainings, and this is considered an ongoing project.⁹ Moreover, the equality officers have regular training on equality at the University of Iceland, which includes presentation on the Professional Council, responses to GBV, and how people can report GBV. This training has been provided for new staff members, new PhD candidates, and students in certain disciplines (delivered upon request from the deans). The equality officers have also been asked to provide training for certain units and have a #MeToo emphasis – for example, especially for men on how they can contribute to a positive change in the work culture and be allies to women.

⁴ https://english.hi.is/university/university_of_iceland_equality_action_plan

⁵ https://english.hi.is/university/rules_of_procedure_on_the_response_to_gender_related_and_sexual_harassment_and_other

⁶ University of Iceland (2018b, 8 February) #MeToo „Í skugga valdsins: konur í vísindum“ Aðgerðaaætlun Háskóla Íslands [#MeToo In shadow of power: women in sciences. University of Iceland's action plan].

⁷ https://english.hi.is/university/university_of_iceland_equality_action_plan

⁸ https://english.hi.is/university/equality_and_diversity_at_the_university_of_iceland

⁹ University of Iceland (2018b, 8 February) #MeToo 'Í skugga valdsins: konur í vísindum' Aðgerðaaætlun Háskóla Íslands (#MeToo in the shadow of power: women in the sciences. University of Iceland's action plan).

The equality officers also annually deliver training on equality issues, including GBV, to first- and third-year students studying the health sciences (all disciplines).

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

The University of Iceland acknowledges that they have a role to provide knowledge on equality and gender, including GBV, in accordance with the requirements of Act No. 150/2020 on Equal Status and Equal Rights Irrespective of Gender. The status of the implementation of the requirement to educate all students on equality and gender was mapped in the University of Iceland in accordance with the #MeToo Action Plan. Suggestions for improvement were presented by the Division of Academic Affairs and the Pro-Rector of Teaching in spring 2019. In accordance with the #MeToo Action Plan, a working group delivered suggestions on how to secure that knowledge on equality issues is part of the teachers and management education of the university. In the year 2021–2022, there were courses on violence offered in four study programmes: nursing, social services, law, and anthropology. However, only the courses in law and social services mention GBV. GBV is also regularly discussed in the University of Iceland’s academic community. This is evident from the large number of events on the #MeToo movement organised by research centres, such as MARK – the Centre for Diversity and Gender Research and RIKK – the Institute for Gender, Equality and Difference, and by faculties, such as the Faculty of Sociology and Anthropology and the Faculty of History and Philosophy.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The three policies combined cover **four** forms of violence, namely GBV, sexual violence, sexual harassment and gender-based harassment. All three policies cover GBV, sexual harassment, and gender-based harassment, while only the Rules of Procedure and the #MeToo Action Plan cover sexual violence.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: Jointly, the three policies cover **6Ps:** Prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services, and policy. Only partnerships are not addressed by any of the three policies. All three policies cover prevalence and protection. Additionally, the Rules of Procedure and the #MeToo Action Plan fulfil the criteria of policy, while the Equality Action Plan and the #MeToo Action Plan cover prevention. Both the Equality Action Plan and the Rules of Procedure cover prosecution. Only the Rules of Procedure cover the provision of services.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups: All three policies address **all target groups**, namely academic staff, non-academic staff, and students. Additionally, others involved in university operations are also addressed in the Rules of Procedure, while the #MeToo Action Plan covers employees of subcontractors.

Intersectionality addressed: The three policies do not address intersectionality. However, in reference to the Equality Action Plan the equality officer notes that even though intersectionality is not clearly stated in the document, the action plan has been developed from an intersectional perspective. Moreover, some actions such as training are implemented with an intersectional perspective.

Specific vulnerable groups: The Equality Action Plan is the only document to address specific vulnerable groups, with **seven** groups defined: Early-career researchers, students and staff with disabilities, students and staff with a migration background, and LGBTQIA+ students and staff. The plan also includes (in the 'other' category) the following statement: 'Discrimination on the basis of sex, gender, skin colour, disability, sexual orientation, gender identity, ethnicity, body shape, age, health, religion, views, residence status, financial means, nationality, race, or culture is prohibited at the University of Iceland'.

Bystanders addressed: Yes, the Equality Action Plan addresses bystanders. More specifically, the 'role' section discusses the obligation of people to report sexual harassment, gender-based and sexual violence, and other forms of violence and bullying, of which they have a reasonable suspicion or knowledge.

Role of perpetrators addressed: No.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: Yes. The Equality Action Plan and the #MeToo Action Plan both define indicators for prevalence, prevention, and protection, and the Equality Action Plan also prosecution. The Rules of Procedure do not address indicators.

According to the national report, indicators defined in the Equality Action Plan are the following. For prevalence, the indicator is publishing the results of surveys of the prevalence and characteristics of sexual harassment, bullying, and other types of violence at the University of Iceland. For prevention, there is an implicit indicator related to the provision of training. For protection, the indicator is again implicit and relates to the publication of resources on how to report

GBV on the UI website and channels. For prosecution, the indicator is also implicit and entails the creation of a framework and procedural rules.

In the #MeToo Action Plan, the indicators are the following: For prevalence, the execution of research and presentation of findings. For prevention, the submission of suggestions for improvement; the provision of training. For protection, changes to the teaching evaluation survey, changes to the Code of Ethics, changes to the reporting process and changes to the procedures.

Monitoring: Yes. Only the Rules of Procedure define monitoring in the form of the number of cases and the outcomes, which are annually monitored.

Evaluation: Yes. Both the Equality Action Plan and the Rules of Procedure use evaluation, while the #MeToo Action plan does not.

The Equality Action Plan evaluates the efficacy of the plan, which results in a staff survey of the effectiveness and efficacy of the implemented projects. According to the equality officer, the policy is assessed at the end of the policy period. The assessment is activities-based (rather than outcome or outputs-based). For the last policy, two-thirds of the activities were fulfilled, and one-third were partly fulfilled - that is, they were ongoing but not finished in time. The responsible actors are the Division of Human Resources in consultation with the school's equal rights committees and human resources managers.

For the Rules of Procedure, the internal auditor made an evaluation on the work culture and human resources at UI that included the Professional Council, which was published in April 2020. The internal auditor of the UI is the responsible actor.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

The Rules of Procedure define a single **procedure for all**.

This policy defines: who to contact, how to report, the investigation process, responsible persons/units, and outcomes.

Who to contact and how to report: Anyone wishing to submit a complaint regarding an offence committed against them, either currently ongoing or in the past, by a staff member or student at the University of Iceland or anyone wishing to report an offence of which they have reasonable suspicion or knowledge shall contact one of the three members of the Professional Council or the UI equality officer. UI staff members may also contact their immediate superior. If this individual is the one who is accused of having committed the offence, the staff member may turn to the superior's superior. Students may also contact their faculty dean or, depending on the circumstances, their school dean. Anyone receiving such a complaint or report shall immediately refer the matter to the Professional Council for processing.

Responsible persons/units: The Professional Council.

Description of the investigation and outcomes: Upon receiving a complaint or report of an offence, the Professional Council shall summon the accused to a meeting to examine his/her position regarding the complaint or report. If a report is submitted by an individual other than the assumed victim of the offence, the Council summons the assumed victim to a meeting to examine their position on the report. Following these interviews with the parties to the case, the Council determines whether the case will be formally processed. The Council has unrestricted access to pertinent files in the university and faculty archives. If the Council decides to formally process a

case, it notifies the supervisors of the academic or work units of the parties to the case. Having consulted with the Council, the supervisors shall take any measures that may be necessary relating to the academic or work arrangements of the parties to the case. Efforts shall be made to reach an agreement regarding work arrangements while the matter is under review. The complainant or assumed victim of the offence may not be transferred to another position because of gender-based or sexual harassment or violence without having requested this her/himself. The Council shall thoroughly investigate the matter, e.g. by interviewing the parties involved and, where appropriate, their co-workers or other individuals who may be able to shed light on the case. The Professional Council shall offer the assumed victim professional assistance from a psychologist, social worker or a therapist. Should the person in question wish to report the matter to the police, the Professional Council shall assist in this as far as possible. After the investigation is concluded, the Council issues an observation outlining its conclusions to the parties involved and to their supervisors. Should the Council deem that an offence has been committed, it will submit a proposal to the supervisor of the relevant academic or work unit concerning an appropriate response. The supervisor will then determine the most appropriate course of action, in consultation with the Division of Human Resources or the Student Counselling and Career Centre. The final decision in such cases shall be taken in accordance with the law and UI regulations. Unless the law dictates otherwise, the Professional Council and others involved are required to treat individual cases as confidential.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Finnborg S. Steinþórsdóttir in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

